

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report #2 for TEBT-2025-0020

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Reporting Quality of Systematic Review Protocols in Environmental and Occupational Toxicology: A meta-epidemiology study
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0020
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration of Interests	This manuscript is an official publication of the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC). The Handling Editor is Editor-in-Chief of EBT and also a contractor for EBTC where, in both roles, they are responsible for ensuring that EBTC publications comply with the standards and goals of the Collaboration. The Handling Editor was also responsible for the policies on systematic reviews at Environment International, which feature prominently in the manuscript. These are viewed as managed interests, where publisher and EBTC policies to minimise the risk of these interests compromising the handling of the manuscript have been followed.
Number of Reviewers	1 editor + 3 peer-reviewers
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Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of the data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies. Prophy.ai was used to identify suitable peer-reviewers for the manuscript.
Recommendation	Revise ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

This manuscript analyses the reporting quality of systematic review protocols that are concerned with the health effects of chemical exposures.

The data collection and analysis methods follow the plan described in the accepted protocol ([Pavlovic et al. 2025](#)) and the authors have provided a discussion that is concordant with the data they have collected.

The comments from the handling editor and reviewers mainly focus on further developing the discussion of the results of the study, as there is a lot more that could be said that would also be justified.

Seriousness of issues identified with write-up of study	The issues are not limitations as such, more an opportunity to further develop the work that has been done.
Potential additional work to overcome issues	Some additional data collection and analysis, and some further discussion with reference to related literature have been recommended. This could take 3-4 days, in my estimation.
Acceptability of characterising limitations instead of additional data collection and analysis	If the authors did not have capacity to do this extra work then the manuscript is already effectively publishable, but it would be a lost opportunity not to do it.

Reviewers' Comments

Note about reviewer comments: Reviewer comments have been aggregated into the structured feedback below by the handling editor. Comments may have been edited for constructiveness or continuity, or annotated to indicate how the authors may consider responding. Comments are numbered for ease of reference.

1. Overall impressions of the manuscript

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

1. This manuscript is well-written, and the methods appropriate for the stated purpose.
2. I would appreciate more detail on the key findings highlighted in the abstract. These findings are described with minimal supporting details in the text.
3. This manuscript reports an assessment of the quality of systematic review protocols in the fields of environmental and occupational toxicology. The manuscript is well-written and provides insightful details into environmental / occupational toxicological protocols. I have highlighted a few areas in which further context and/or detail would be helpful, especially for areas that are highlighted in the abstract but are only minimally referenced in the text.

Reviewer 3

4. Authors are presenting an overview of the reporting quality of systematic review protocols in environmental and occupational toxicology research. The manuscript is concise, clear, and cohesive.

2. Are the introduction, rationale, and hypotheses the same as in the accepted protocol?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 1

5. Yes, the authors adhered to their planned methods. Where they deviated slightly, they described thoroughly in the Deviations from the Protocol section (2.5).

3. Were the collected data able to test the stated hypotheses by satisfying the approved outcome-neutral conditions?

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 3

6. Adherence to the PRISMA-P checklist is a simple yet effective approach for assessing reporting quality.
7. Why were protocols on PROSPERO and similar platforms not eligible? The preceding protocol for this work suggests that reasons may include difficulties in searching PROSPERO or a lack of peer-review of protocols published to online platforms. Elaboration and justification regarding this inclusion criterion are lacking.

4. Are the additional post-hoc or exploratory analyses (if any) added by the authors justified, methodologically sound, and informative?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

There were no additional unplanned analyses. There is some additional data collection and light analysis suggested by the reviewers in the next section of this report - the authors should be careful to make it clear that this is additional to the original protocol (which I am sure they will do).

5. Are the authors' findings, based on the planned and unplanned analyses, justified?

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

The reviewers largely agree that what is discussed is justified. What the reviewers are asking for is more development of the implications of the findings, as there is a lot more that could be said that would also be justified. As there are lots of comments to respond to, the authors may wish to develop a list of discussion points based on the reviewers' suggestions and use this to structure their response to reviewer comments (and the development of the discussion section in the manuscript).

Some of the comments may require some additional data collection, but most of it does not look too onerous and could significantly improve the manuscript.

Just reflecting on this, I wonder if the two primary issues raised by the reviewer comments might be:

(a) If the authors could find out if peer-review makes a protocol better-reported? It may not: if the journal review process is not sufficiently rigorous then journal-published protocols may not be much better than PROSPERO registrations, but they should be a bit better. This would be important, as it would suggest peer-review makes a difference, just not a big difference (or possibly, big enough difference if preregistration is supposed to more-or-less guarantee a very rigorous final review). I wouldn't ask the authors to do any additional data collection and analysis, but if they could find studies of the quality of PROSPERO registrations, that should at least provide a point of comparison.

(b) Since there are several Environment International protocols included in the authors' study, and we know EI is particularly exacting when it comes to SR standards, could these be looked at as a subgroup in a secondary analysis, and see if there is a suggestive difference? This would just be an additional secondary analysis to support discussion and hypothesising.

Reviewer comments

Editor (from triage, prior to peer-review)

8. The discussion is well-written but could perhaps be further developed, especially around the knowledge gaps left by the study - what it is we don't know in relation to the quality of systematic review protocols in toxicology, and how future research could address these. I think this is important because the authors have investigated a very indirect measure of the quality of a SRP. While they did this for good reason, it does put quite tight constraints on what can be learned from this study and makes it harder to connect to broader concerns about the quality of research (we know that SRPs are reported reasonably well, but what that tells us seems quite limited).
9. Just thinking about this, obviously SRPs are still quite rare (if there was some valid way of estimating how many journal-published SRs there are compared to journal-published SRPs, that might be helpful), and we know how well reported they are but not how valid the planned methods are. We also don't know about the impact of the journal-published SRP on the final quality of SRs - and it is quality we should ultimately be interested in (this is the difference with the Menon paper - there, we looked at a closer proxy for rigour

than reporting quality, and as follow-up work this paper looked at something easier to study but is a bit less revealing about SRP quality).

10. Some discussion of these issues, and the sort of research that should be done to address them, so that this EBTC publication gives a clear steer to the rest of the field, would be welcome, I think. (This should not be perfunctory, the authors should consider in some detail what ought to be done next.)
11. In addition to the 2016 publication where we introduced our plans for SRs at Environment International, [in 2022 Nicolas Roth and I reflected on how well our plans were working and what we had learned](#). This might be of interest to the authors, and may be a relevant citation for para 1 of the Discussion (though do not take this as instruction to include it!). This may also give the authors some ideas about how to discuss the issues of whether and how the quality of SRPs might impact the quality of SRs, and how this could be investigated.

Reviewer 1

12. I appreciated the clarity of the discussion section, and I believe that it did an excellent job of not overstating or overgeneralizing findings. I particularly liked the paragraph on funding (beginning line 377), because it tied in the findings from this research with findings from other research and also provided a message about what could be done/why it is important. I would suggest that the authors consider strengthening their discussion section with additional reflection and comparison to other research to see where findings diverged, where they were similar to other work, and what lessons can be drawn from the new additions from this research. [I have highlighted] a few areas that I thought could potentially benefit from additional discussion.
13. I am very interested in the authors' thoughts on whether full protocols should always be published as journal articles, or whether study registration (with fields like those in PROSPERO, which aligns with PRISMA-P) meets the goals of a protocol. Should more people be encouraged to publish full protocols as journal articles? Why? Is there any research on protocols that are journal articles vs. registrations that you could comment on? Will people who go through the effort of publishing a full protocol be more likely to adhere to their protocol and/or report their findings better later, for example? I believe

literature exists on comparing protocols for RCTs in various sources, for example, that may provide some insight. I am curious about this primarily because we don't often recommend publishing a full protocol, but perhaps we should. **[Editor:** I expect there is research on e.g. completeness of PRISMA registrations, and I also expect that completeness of PRISMA registrations is inconsistent. Peer-review should, in theory, improve the completeness of a protocol - but it might not improve them by much, so the implications of that for journal policy could be developed. For example, at EBT and Environment International, compliance with standards is the responsibility of the editor, it is not left entirely to peer-reviewers because of the uneven results of doing this. Environment International just [updated a previous editorial](#) that may touch on this issue. Discussion within the limits of what the authors have found would be welcome.]

14. Though this research focuses on reporting quality, and not methodological quality, the discussion section could be used to further discuss existing evidence of how reporting quality can impact or suggest shortcomings with methodological quality. There are several studies that look at reporting (usually PRISMA) and also use AMSTAR, for example, that may be good to discuss.
15. Are there any comparisons with literature that looks at other types of protocol (e.g., SPIRIT) that would be useful?
16. Are there journals that are more successful in implementing protocol publication than others?
17. Paragraph lines 372-376: I believe there is significantly more literature on this topic (including checklist but not being compliant with it) out there, and perhaps specifically on SPIRIT or other protocol reporting guidelines that could be interesting to discuss in more depth.
18. It may be helpful to further speculate on specific research that should be done to follow up on this work. What research do you think would be key next steps for the toxicology community to take on? Why? What will they add to the literature? I realize there is one sentence in the conclusions, but you may wish to add more information in the Discussion that directly leads to these future lines of work. **[Editor:** This seems a good suggestion -

the original concept for this EBTC research was somewhat broader and more focused on understanding the quality of SR protocols and the relationship with the quality of final SRs, though of course plans changed, and during my triage checks I thought more could be done in the discussion to interpret the findings.]

Reviewer 2

19. In general, the authors should verify that conclusions are well-supported by the reported results. I've added some specifics below where the authors might reassess if there might be additional information to support the observations/conclusions.
20. Line 163: Why 4 reviewers?
21. Line 243: Is exclusion of >98% records typical? Can you provide context on whether this is high or typical?
22. Line 258/Figure 2. Its interesting that the number of published protocols in these fields has declined since 2021. This finding is mentioned in abstract but not the discussion. I think this warrants being addressed in the discussion. In the authors' opinion, what might be possible underlying reasons for this trend?
23. Lines 283-291: Can you provide more explicit details on how the reader should interpret these findings? The SRP is quite broad, so its hard to draw any insights from the list of outcomes presented here. Please add details to help the reader interpret this information on studied outcomes. What knowledge can be drawn from this analysis?
24. Table 3: Why are the types not always listed in logical (descending) order? For example, the types of "Outcomes per Organ System" are not listed in descending order.
25. Lines 303-304: Please say more regarding how often the role of funder/sponsor was reported, especially since this finding is referenced in the abstract.
26. Lines 369-371: I do not see any reference in the results that analyze protocols by journal. This could be interesting and I would like to hear more. I suggest adding this analysis to the results, or not discussing it as part of the discussion section.

Reviewer 3

27. It would have been interesting to gain an understanding of the proportion of SR protocols relative to published SR in the field (or a relevant subfield), rather than merely the absolute number of protocols. Authors may consider adding estimates to their discussion section, to help readers contextualize findings.
28. Also, the implications of not including grey literature like PROSPERO protocols should be addressed in the limitations section, as this and similar platforms are extremely popular for registering protocols, by explicitly discussing the potential effects on the current overview findings (e.g., regarding selection bias), rather than simply stating that grey literature was not included.
29. The discussion paragraph on the importance of disclosing funder roles is important. Authors may elaborate in the discussion section on why reporting quality matters for systematic review protocols in toxicology research- what is the current context of evidence syntheses in the toxicology research field, and what can be recommended? Some questions for sparking ideas:
- a. Why are protocols so important especially right now, relative to current systematic review practices and developments (e.g., large-scale and cross-disciplinary consortia, automation and AI in evidence synthesis, etc...)
 - b. What specific aspects of systematic reviews of occupational and environmental toxicology research make pre-specified protocols with high reporting quality so important? For instance, it may be especially important to pre-specify risk of bias assessment methods for systematic reviews of observational studies. For example, specifying lists of confounders/ co-exposures/ covariates of interest, acceptable exposure assessment methods, and other quality indicators may require greater review team involvement, planning, detailed documentation, etc. compared to assessing analogous study processes in experimental studies (e.g., randomization), to ensure both i) appropriate methods and ii) correct implementation by the review team- all facilitated via comprehensive protocols. Further, methodological approaches may arguably have especially impactful

implications for systematic reviews of observational studies- making comprehensive protocols all the more important.

6. Other comments

Reviewer comments

Editor (from triage, prior to peer-review)

30. In Appendix B3 (Included protocols) I noticed that “Environment International” is misspelled once as “Environmental International”, creating a count of 10 rather than 11 occurrences for the journal in the dataset. This does not appear to have affected the results, but the authors should check to make sure no coding errors have occurred that affect the counts in their data (it will affect the reusability of their data).

Reviewer 1

31. I wasn't sure how lines 356-361 followed the prior paragraph. It seems like it could be its own paragraph, perhaps with expanded detail.

32. Do you have any thoughts on why NAMs were included so rarely?

33. For the paragraph beginning on line 395, I think it would be helpful to say 'Data management procedures **“(Q6)”** ... 'Data extraction **“(Q8)”** procedure... and then "This could be partially explained by our assessment approach, where **“these”** two items..."

34. The authors note that they found SRPs where the confidence in the body of evidence was not addressed, and specifically that there may be "unawareness of toxicology-specific risk of bias and evidence integration tools", but there is no mention of what those tools are. Could something be added to highlight which tools are toxicology-specific? [Editor: [This EBTC paper](#) may be helpful for this, although I note I am one of the authors and am not requiring the authors to cite it, just alerting them to it as a resource.]

35. Could you note the domain that Frost's article was in as part of the paragraph beginning on line 406? It might help to give slightly more context for that. I specifically noted that

Frost's article title says protocols were inadequate, but you didn't really comment on how your findings differ substantially, e.g., so that may be helpful to add as well.

36. I appreciate the authors' commitment to clear reporting, and I deeply appreciate the authors' attention to detail in reporting the search. There are two items where additional information is required for complete reporting, however: item 1 (database names) and item 2 (multi-database searching).

a. Item 1: Please state which platform was used to search Embase. If it was Embase via Embase.com, it is sufficient to say Embase.com instead of Embase, though ideally, please note if you were also searching in Embase Classic and/or Preprints; if it was Embase via Ovid, please make sure to report the full database name (e.g., Embase, Preprint, Clinical Trials and Embase Classic* 1947 – Present, updated daily). If you are using Embase.com and are not sure whether your institution has access to Embase Classic and/or Preprints as part of your subscription, and/or whether they are automatically searched by default, you can check by going to the Advanced search and then Sources. If you have Embase Classic available, it will be listed as a source. I presume that you searched PubMed via PubMed.gov and not via a 3 party tool like EndNote, but if you searched it a different way, please indicate that. Scopus is only searchable via Scopus.com and its API; if you used the API, though I don't believe you did, please indicate that.

b. Item 2: Web of Science is a platform, not a database, so you did search multiple databases simultaneously (each institution has unique subscriptions and default search settings for this tool, so it is critical to list the databases individually). The easiest way to do this is if you have an export of the search strategy that you saved when you ran the search, as it lists the institution's entitlements for that search and whether you only searched within specific databases. For example:

Entitlements:

- WOS.IC: 1993 to 2026
- WOS.CCR: 1985 to 2026
- WOS.SCI: 1900 to 2026
- WOS.AHCI: 1975 to 2026
- WOS.BHCI: 2005 to 2026

- WOS.BSCI: 2005 to 2026
- WOS.ESCI: 2021 to 2026
- WOS.ISTP: 1990 to 2026
- WOS.SSCI: 1900 to 2026
- WOS.ISSHP: 1990 to 2026

If you are searching in more than the Core Collection, you may need to look for both your Core Collection entitlements AND the All Databases entitlements.

A longer way to do this is if you go to the Advanced Search page. Look at the box that says "Search in:" and "Collections:" Most likely, it will be at your institution's default search. Click on the caret next to each, and you will be able to see the complete list and full names of the multiple databases you searched. Again, if All Databases is the default search, you will also need to look at the Core Collection databases by selecting Core Collection from the Search in: area.

37. In the manuscript, it says that you searched on Dec. 6, 2024, but in the supplementary files, it has different dates for the searches. Was the final search run on Dec. 6? If so, I would suggest updating the supplementary files.
38. Line 109, "this issue": Is "this issue" the methodological and reporting quality of SR? Or the lack of protocols and compromised reporting quality of SRP? I wasn't quite sure.
39. This is for my own knowledge, but for Q6, data management, was the software/platform you were looking for regarding the search how it was deduplicated, primarily? I wasn't entirely sure.
40. Line 281, "Pesticides were a common focus": It seems like it wasn't common, comparatively? Perhaps just "focus" instead of "common focus"?
41. Line 294: Please cite ROSES and COSTER; some readers may not be familiar with them or what they are. You may wish to spell them out in an abbreviations section, though this is not necessary.

42. Table 3: Academia is missing a % after 76; chemicals is capitalized in Industrial chemicals
43. Line 354: Respiratory and nervous systems?
44. Line 426-33: You may want to cite something that discusses the differentiation between reporting and methodological quality. (And note perhaps, that, conversely, of course, if something is poorly reported, it is possible that it was of high methodological quality.)
45. Line 442: Instead of “improvement in data...”, I would suggest, “improvement in reporting data...”
46. I appreciate all efforts to improve the reporting quality of systematic reviews (and their protocols), and I thank the authors for their efforts in highlighting this issue and the importance of clear and robustly reported protocols. I am happy to see this work published as a registered report, as often meta-research does not adhere to the standards which it advocates—this paper 100% does. I especially appreciated the detailed information on changes to the protocol, the data and code availability, and of course, the high quality of the reporting. I would like to see more detail on the differences between full published protocols and preregistered protocols, as well as a few other points listed above.

Reviewer 2

47. In the introduction, the timeliness of the background information should be reassessed. As an example, line 95 cites that registration of SRP are recognized as an important step in the SR process yet this step is frequently omitted, with citation to a 2009 article. Fifteen years in the field of systematic review seems sufficiently long for me to question if this finding is still valid currently (ie, is protocol registration still frequently omitted?).

7. Comments on summary sections

Editor’s summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

No reviewer comments.

8. Minor issues

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 2

In section 2.3 – are abbreviations (SHE, MPA, etc) referring to individual authors? I'm not sure this level of attribution is needed/best practice. Again, line 200-201 and 235, not sure this level of attribution is needed.

The structure of this evaluation report is based on the reviewer and author guidelines for Registered Reports (Chambers et al. 2023, <https://osf.io/pukzy>).